

THE JUPITER PROJECT

A project to develop electronic medical record software using the Jupiter SDI (Software Development Infrastructure). This is a proprietary set of tools developed by Jupiter with **exclusive access**.

Medical errors rank behind heart disease and cancer as the THIRD LEADING CAUSE OF DEATH in the U.S., Johns Hopkins researchers say. ...

Based on an analysis of prior research, the Johns Hopkins study estimates that **more than 250,000 Americans die each year from medical errors.**

THE JUPITER PROJECT has designed a **secret proprietary man machine interfaces** (how you interact with the software) based on state of the art cognitive psychology and Scientific discoveries which **has completely eliminated the medical errors which are ranked third in leading cause of death** behind heart disease and cancer. **Labs using the Jupiter system** over the last 20 years **are now the top labs in the world** and **since have a record of zero medical errors due to medical record system clerical errors.** One lab being the **HLA lab at MD Anderson Cancer Center in Houston.**

The purpose of **THE JUPITER PROJECT** is to **very easily**
develop electronic medical record systems specifically
designed to **meet the unique and specific needs** of each
different customer.

OUR TWO MAIN ASSETS

- **An internal product that is going to be very valuable**, we are going to have a product that we are not going to sell and we are not going to patent because then we would have to disclose what it is and how it works, and we don't want to do that because then people will be able to copy it. and patents are very difficult to enforce.
- **We have a service only we can provide, which is the development of customized electronic medical record systems** specifically designed to meet the unique and specific needs of each different customer, created in a matter of a few weeks to a few months using our internal product the **Jupiter SDI**.

THE JUPITER PROJECT offers **a variety of products for medical centers and laboratories. Each** product is **created custom from scratch using the Jupiter SDI infrastructure**, tailored with the **customer's specific needs** in mind.

What we are going to sell is **our services to develop these customized medical record systems.**

With this infrastructure (**Jupiter SDI**), these customized electronic medical record systems can be developed in weeks or a few months by a few programmers, **opposed** to hundreds of programmers working for years.

Cerner and **Epic** create messy giant medical record systems that take years to build by hundreds of programmers at a cost of hundreds of millions of dollars.

Jupiter can develop a totally new clean robust system in 6-12 weeks with our secret know how (**Jupiter SDI**) by a few programmers.

The real value of our company is our secret know how of this computer infrastructure. (Jupiter SDI)

This secret technical know how to develop electronic medical record systems is based on the following.

These are our assets:

All assets are proprietary, secret, exclusive and developed by Jupiter.

1. Object oriented programming libraries (computer libraries)
2. Code Machines- Computer programs that write computer code.
3. The **most efficient and robust data structures that have already been tested in many applications over two decades.** These are kept secret and are the foundation of the success of everything we do. This is the foundation and the core of our ability to develop the best electronic medical record systems on the market.
4. The algorithms used are based on machine learning techniques, **sophisticated pattern recognition using publicly known and proprietary secret artificial intelligence tools.**
5. Man machine interfaces (how you interact with the software) based on state of the art cognitive psychology and Scientific discoveries (this is also a **secret and proprietary feature of our products and it is the key to prevent the kind of clerical errors that are very common in health care and can cause great expenses and damage to patients)**)

Competitive Advantage

Jupiter can develop a totally new system in **6-12 weeks** with our secret know how by **a few programmers**.

The system developed by **Jupiter SDI** is **customized to the customer's needs** opposed to a one size fits all software that is currently the case. (Ex: Cerner, Epic)

Because the system can be developed in a few weeks to a few months by a few programmers **opposed** to years with hundreds of programmers, the cost per system is drastically less than the competition.

Example:

Cerner and Epic System cost for Major Hospital - \$500 Million - \$1 Billion

Jupiter cost for a Major Hospital - \$10 Million - \$30 Million

Competitive Advantage Continued

THE JUPITER PROJECT secret proprietary man machine interface (how you interact with the software), based on state of the art cognitive psychology and Scientific discoveries which have been successfully used in several labs over the past two decades to prevent the kind of clerical errors that are very common in health care and can cause great expenses and damage to patients. **Due to this new interface the labs using them are now the top labs in the world and have eliminated errors that can even cause the life of a patient.** One lab being the HLA lab at MD Anderson Cancer Center in Houston